

DESIGN, ANALYSIS AND CERTIFICATION OF THE COMPOSITE WING FOR THE EXPERIMENTAL AIRCRAFT X31A

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ABSTRACT

For the exploration of the flight maneuver regime beyond the traditional aerodynamic stall barrier two experimental aircrafts for the X-series, the X-31A, were designed, manufactured and flight tested under a joint US/German development program.

Design and manufacturing processes focussed on the short timeframe and limited budget available and at the same time had to accomodate as many „off the shelf“ system components as possible. The design principals and analysis criteria for the german workshare, the composite wing structure including the all composite leading- and trailing-edge flaps are shown together with the composite material substansation. The certification approach for the experimental aircrafts, leading from subcomponent testing to full-scale proofload testing and in-flight monitoring of the wing structure is explained.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The X31A experimental aircraft was developed as a joint venture between Rockwell International in El Segundo, California and Daimler Benz Aerospace AG (The former Messerschmitt- Bölkow- Blohm, MBB) in Munich, Germany during 1986 and 1990 and made its maiden flight on October 11th, 1991 in Palmdale, California.

The program evolved from the work at MBB in the late 70's focusing on an extension of the usable angle of attack α - regime of fighter aircraft beyond the aerodynamic stall limitations at $c_{a_{max}}$ during maneuvering.

For the first time ever this would allow an aircraft to maneuver into and safely recover from the post-stall regime during a controlled maneuver, Fig. 1.

The ratio between the allowable, trimmed α for maneuvering and the α $c_{a_{max}}$ for conventional fighter aircraft is 0.5 - 0.8 which means that only 50 -80% of the potential wing lift can be utilized during maneuvers. Often the lack of directional stability and yaw control authority due to the reduced vertical fin

Fig 1 Typical Post-Stall Maneuver

effectivity is the major contributing factor to these angle of attack restrictions.

Fig.2 X-31A Experimental Aircraft

Early simulations at the IABG-Testcenter in Munich indicated an α -ratio of 2.0, requiring trimmed flight in a 70deg. angle of attack regime would dramatically increase the maneuverability of fighter aircraft if controlled pitch- and roll- maneuvers are feasible along the velocity vector of the aircraft by reducing turn radii and increase turn rates [1].

At this time the requirement for vectored engine thrust to provide directional control authority was defined as part of the program.

In 1983 Rockwell International joined the efforts and established its own program to study the requirements for a demonstrator vehicle. A configuration of a subsonic vehicle called SNAKE (Super Normal Altitude Kinetic Enhancement) was tested in the NASA-Langley windtunnel including first demonstrations of vectored thrust by compressed air [2].

In 1986 a MOU was signed between DARPA, USA and the German BMVG to develop, certify and test an experimental aircraft with increased maneuverability, the X-31A, Fig.2.

2.0 CONFIGURATION AND WORKSHARE

The single seat / single engine configuration features a low delta wing with a double canted leading edge, an aspect ratio of 2.3 and inner/outer trailing edge flaps moving simultaneously for pitch and roll control. The three individually driven vector vanes are positioned aft of the engine nozzle to deflect the thrust in a 360 deg. rotational cone by max. 15 deg. The lower two vanes can be deployed 60 deg. outboard to act as additional airbrakes.

Other main characteristics are:

- * Thrust to weight ratio greater 1.0 at mil. power
- * Rectangular engine inlet with variable lower inlet lip for $\alpha > 45$ deg.
- * Unrestricted engine operation at $\alpha = 70$ deg. and $M=0.1$, 20000 ft.
- * Low wing load 270 kg/m² (64.5 lb/ft²) at design gross weight
- * Configuration layout unstable in pitch at subsonic speed
- * Canards act as horizontal control surface and can provide „Nose Down pitch moment“ throughout the flight envelope
- * Fail safe digital flight control system
- * Recovery from spin possible without thrust vectoring
- * „Post Stall“-display (Head-Up and/or helmet mounted) to enhance pilots awareness during maneuvering
- * Various „Off the shelf“- equipment used for aircraft systems

The work share between the two main contractors, Rockwell International and Daimler Benz Aerospace, both independently funded by their government agencies lead to the hardware/software responsibilities for DASA shown in Fig. 3.

One major feature of the development phase and throughout the program is the principal of „single source“ for all engineering work at RI and DASA except Software/Hardware interfaces. For example aircraft loads analysis is the responsibility of RI but analysis and design of the wing structure and the certification of the wings are sole responsibility of DASA. Interface loads at wing/fuselage stations were generated in a global analysis model were DASA supplied the wings, RI the fuselage and loads model.

To accelerate engineering data exchange between the two development centers in El Segundo and Munich a global internet system was used for data transmission with paper documents for backup only.

The certification of the DASA workshare was provided by the german authorities while RI- components were certified against US requirements. General aircraft certification was then issued by US-Navy / NASA agencies on the bases of the individual certification statements throughout the program.

Fig.3 DASA Workshare Components

3.0 DESIGN PRINCIPALS, MATERIALS, ANALYSIS CRITERIA

3.1 DESIGN PRINCIPALS

The design principals and analysis criteria for the experimental X31- A were tailored to the specific program needs in order to avoid time consuming studies and evaluations within the program. Using the already available technologies and sources on both sides for their workshare made the stringent time and budget limitations possible without compromising quality and safety of the aircraft.

This approach naturally lead to a „Multi-material, multi design criteria“- aircraft where similar components show the application of different design concepts, materials and analysis criteria build to different manufacturing- and QA- specifications.

A special statement in the program contract enabled this engineering approach and specified the rules for simplification of procedures and requirements. Fig.4 indicates the major aircraft design requirements.

Fig. 5 shows the overall dimensions and specific design principals for the wing structure with an almost triangular planform using a 5% transonic airfoil with two leading edges hinged to the front spar and two trailing edges hinged to the rear spar. All control surfaces are individually driven by hydraulic actuators. Since the X-31A carries its entire fuel of approx. 3400 lbs in the center fuselage there are no provisions for tanks in the wing structure.

Parameter	Requirement
V_{Max}	M 0.9 at 35000 ft
NZ_{limt}	+7.33/-3.0 g
NX_{limt}	-1.0 g
Design weight	14600 lbs
TV-Operation	M 0.2 at $\alpha = 60$ deg / 20000 ft
Design q	700 psf
Airframe life	300 FH or 400 Flights
Certification code	Mil 8860-series

Fig.4 X-31A Design Requirements

The wing box structure consists of monolithic carbon fibre skins with integrated local reinforcements bolted to the metal substructure using close tolerance bolts in the upper surface and blind rivets for the lower surface. The material chosen for the skins is NARMCO 5245/T800 a bismaleimide modified epoxy system, autoclave cured at 175°C (350°F) and postcured at 195°C (383°F). Unidirectional tapes with a cured thickness of 0.125 mm (0.005 in) were used to allow a high degree of flexibility for laminate lay-ups and to avoid problems like wrinkling in complex contour areas.

Local load introduction areas like wing to fuselage interface fittings or control surface attachments are designed as bolted joints using tension type titanium or CRES-bolts.

The multispar design of the inner structure features machined spars (front-spar, two main-spars and rear-spar) made out of 7000 series aluminum alloys and sheet metal auxiliary spars made from 2024 T42 alloy. All ribs are designed as sheet metal parts except for load introduction areas like trailing edge flap actuator attachments and the root rib.

Wing to fuselage attachment is provided by a total of 4 hinge stations with two main bending attachments and 4 vertical shear attachment devices, Fig.5. Due to the limited life of the airframe 7050 T7451 high strength aluminum alloy is used instead of titanium or steel. The interface area is covered by fairings made of honeycomb with woven graphite epoxy prepreg material FIBREDUX 913C/T840 for the skins and NOMEX core material.

Unlike other aircraft, the X-31A unstable pitch design requires that control surfaces are constantly moving during flight. The trailing edge flaps are used to stabilize in pitch and roll axes whereas the leading edge flaps provide optimum airflow over the wing at higher angles of attack, $\alpha > 15^\circ$. Both leading edge flaps always move together, driven by a common hydraulic/mechanical actuation system. The inboard and outboard trailing edge flaps are independently actuated by a pair of linear hydraulic actuators.

All flaps show a monolithic composite design with CFC-skins, integrated ribs, bolted-in metal spars and load introduction fittings. Local reinforcements of the CFC-skins and ribs are distributing the loads from the actuator attachments into the structure.

The material used for the control surfaces is identical with the wingbox skins, NARMCO 5245/T800. Machined flap spars and fittings are made from aluminum alloys like 7475 T7351 and bolted to the skin and ribs using close tolerance titanium fasteners.

All integrated CFC ribs are cobonded to the precured skins using high temperature film adhe-

Fig.5 Wing Dimensions and Layout

Fig.6 Typical section through Trailing Edge Flap

sive BSL 322A in a single autoclave process. Fig.6 shows a typical section of a trailing edge flap with the upper and lower skin plies continuing around the trailing edge tip thus avoiding the additional endsplice. A nonstructural end cap with high density foam and two plies of CFC prepreg is bonded to the tip.

3.2 ANALYSIS CRITERIA

For the composite structure the analysis criteria used for design are shown in Fig.7. and take the environmental effects of composite material behavior and its sensitivity to low energy impact damage into account.

A selections of design allowables for unidirectional tape material for the wing skin is given in Fig.8, used during strength analysis for ultimate load conditions.

While the elastic modulus E_{11} and E_{22} quoted as *Strength* are average statistical values and also averaged for compression /

tension loading for the *Stability* analysis B-basis values for compression and shear loading are used to predict the buckling onset of laminates, thus

- *Static strength analysis „worst case“ environmental conditions, 80°C/100°C, 85% rel. humidity
- *Safety factor of 1.5 on Limit Loads
- *Linear elastic laminate theory for composites
- *Design in unnotched areas against max. fibre strain in any direction
- *Notched composite analysis and bearing loads with superpositioned bypass loading
- *All composite skins designed nonbuckling at Ultimate load
- *Symmetric layup of all skin panels, equal No. of +45 and -45 plies
- *Min. 3 ply-directions with fibres in the main loading direction
- *Max. of 4 plies stacked together in one direction
- *No interference fit fasteners in CFC material, min. pitch is 4 x dia.

Fig.7 Design criteria for composites

<i>Allowable</i>	<i>Strength</i>	<i>Strength</i>	<i>Stability</i>	<i>Stability</i>	<i>Dimension</i>
	<i>RT</i>	<i>100°C/wet</i>	<i>RT</i>	<i>100°C/Wet</i>	
E_{11}	157500	157500	140000	140000	N/mm ²
E_{22}	9350	8500	8700	7900	N/mm ²
F_{1t}	2400	2200			N/mm ²
F_{1c}	1250	1000			N/mm ²
F_{12}	100	55			N/mm ²

Fig 8 Design allowables for CFC material

treating the stability failure criteria in the same manner as the strength requirement.

4.0 MATERIAL DATA SUBSTANTIATION AND CERTIFICATION PROCEDURE

Although the usage of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (CFC-Epoxy) materials for primary structures contribute to weight and cost savings of complex contoured aircraft components like wingskins, its application to primary structures requires extensive data basis generation and testing for:

- * Mechanical properties and environmental influence
- * Chemical stability and dielectric behavior
- * Manufacturing handling and processing qualities
- * Quality assurance database

Fig.9 gives an overview of the material data program performed to generate allowables for the NARMCO 5245/T800 material used in the wing design.

In order to generate a statistical databasé for multidirectional laminate properties, based on

unidirectional ply data, the Data Collection and Qualification Program (DCQP) was

Fig.9 CFC Uni/Multi-directional Material Data Substantiation

established with the requirement to check for additional variables like lay-ups and environmental effects on the mathematical prediction of multidirectional properties, Fig. 10. As the program showed in some areas of composite design (i.e. notched laminates and „free edges“) even the influence of stacking sequences for one particular lay-up needs to be addressed to generate reliable allowables. Once this database was established the engineering laminate properties were generated and documented in „Carpet Plot“-form.

Property	Layup Type	No. of Lay-ups	No. of -55°C Tests	No. of RT Tests	No. of 80/100°C Tests	Total No. of Specimens
Tensile Strength and Modulus	II, +	2	6/6	6/6	6/6	36
Compression Strength, Modulus	II,+	2	12/6	12/6	12/6	54
Interlaminar Shear	II	1	6	6	6	18
Tensile Strength, Modulus	multi	11	25	40	50	115
Compress. Strength, Modulus	multi	11	25	40	65	130
Inplane Shear strength	multi	3	10	15	35	60
Inplane Shear Modulus	multi	1	3	3	6	12
Notched Tensile	multi	6	15	130	55	200
Notched Compression.	multi	6	30	190	110	330
Double Shear Bearing, On/off Axis	multi	10	30	195	60	285
Single Shear Bearing	multi	5	10	120	30	160
Load Interaction with Bearing	multi	4	-	60	20	80
G1c	II,multi	2	-	15	-	15
Compression after Impact	multi	1	-	9	-	9
Compression Double Taper	multi	10	-	60	60	120
Inplane Shear Modulus	X	1	-	-	20	20
ILSS after Fluid Immersion	II	1	-	70	-	70
Mutiangular Variability	multi	1	-	60	50	110
					Total:	1.788

Fig.10 DCQP- Program for NARMCO 5245C/T800

The structural verification concept used for the X-31A structure based on a combination of analysis/test checks in different stages of the design process for the following disciplines:

- * Aero loads
- * Materials
- * Manufacturing Quality
- * Structure Strength
- * Dynamics

as shown in Fig. 11. The major difference from production development programs was the lack of a full scale static ultimate strength test and fatigue test.

While fatigue testing was discarded due to the short airframe life, the static ultimate test was replaced by separate testing of critical components, a „Proofload“-test of the Aircraft No.1 structure up to 110% Limit load, its calibration for flight loads and „Real time“-loads monitoring during flight envelope expansion. Fig.12 shows the loads envelope for the wing for bending moment and torque and indicates the critical test conditions.

Fig.12 X-31A Wing Loads Envelope

The test article was the structurally complete aircraft, except for certain items replaced by test fixtures to provide proper load distribution during each test. These fixtures include the spin chute attach fittings, thrust vector vanes, main and nose landing gear wheels and shock struts, engine, wing strike control surface actuators. Non-structural components such as fairings and doors were also removed for ease of access.

The tests were performed in the test laboratories of RI, El Segundo at ambient temperature. For testing, the aircraft was supported by fixtures at the main and nose landing gear and the engine mounts. Hydraulic jacks were used in conjunction with whiffletrees, bonded tension pads and shear straps to apply loads to the aircraft, the proof load test setup is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 11. Structural Verification Concept

Load transducers were used to measure both applied and reacted loads. Flight strain gages plus additional ground test gages and deflection gages were read and recorded during each proof load or calibration test. The complete wing and the control surfaces were tested to 110% limit load in four different loading conditions and results from the strain gage measurement were compared to the predictions from the Finite Element model which was run with the test- loads for each condition.

A total of 12 calibration test load conditions were also applied to the wing structure to facilitate the equation system for load data reduction from flight test strain gage readings to wing bending moment, vertical shear and torque at the wing to fuselage interface.

For the trailing and leading edge flaps the actuation system was calibrated off aircraft and the hingemoments for each surface were derived directly from the gages via calibration tables.

All 48 flight gages on CFC-wing components are temperature compensated.

A major structural element that comprises several critical analysis steps and material allowables was tested prior to the full scale proof load test is shown in Fig 14.

The aft main bending attachment of the wing was tested successfully at the DASA structural test facilities in Munich up to 125% ultimate load at ambient temperature, which covers the required „extra strength“ for environmental effects on the composite.

Fig. 13 Proof load Test Setup

Tests were performed for the critical loads envelope of all relevant elements of the attachment:

- * Upper and Lower Main Bending Lugs
- * Integrated Shear Strut
- * Lower Wing skin /fitting Joints

5.0 FLIGHT TEST RESULTS

Flight loads envelope expansion started with Flight No 1-007 on 13.November 1990 and was performed with AC No.1. Basic flightmaneuvers from the conventional envelope like „Wind-up“ turns, „Push overs“, „Full stick rolls“ and „Abrupt pull-ups“ were performed to evaluate the handling performances and the structural behavior of the aircraft. With the loadlevels gradually increasing the local component strains were compared to the proof load level and the calibration equations used to generate section- loads of the wing and hingemoments for the

control surfaces in order to compare against the design envelope loads.

With the continuation of the flight test towards the high- α -regime the test program continued to show excellent coincidence of predicted versus flight loads for the wing structure, the only flight parameter to be restricted for structural reasons were roll entry rates into the poststall regime because of excessive outboard flap hingemoments. All other section loads on the wing and control surfaces during poststall maneuvers were covered by the conventional envelope, however real time loads-monitoring continued throughout the tactical evaluation phase of the program.

On November 6., 1992 a full stick roll maneuver along the flight vector axis was successfully demonstrated at level flight at a flight angle of attack of 70 deg. By April 1993 the entry into the poststall flight from elevated g-maneuvers were demonstrated, 6g- entries into poststall flights and carefree handling of the aircraft in the complete poststall regime were achieved by January 1994.

Tactical maneuvers against comparable conventional aircraft like F-18 and F-16 showed the superior handling and maneuvering capabilities during „close-air“ engagements.

In summer 1994 a total of 122 engagements flown by 6 different pilots from both nations from different starting positions, both offensive for the adversary aircraft and neutral at different speeds had been evaluated and showed the following results [3]:

Defensive Setups

- * 50% X-31A wins
- * 30% F-18 wins
- * 20% Remis

Neutral Setups

- * 91% X-31A wins
- * 3 % F-18 wins
- * 6 % Remis

To better judge the poststall-maneuver advantages, flight tests were performed with the X-31A restricted to the conventional flight envelope. This showed reverse results with the F-18 as the clear winner, emphasising the advantages of poststall maneuvering.

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

The degree of success in designing, building, certifying and testing a technology demonstrator aircraft has been shown by a number of goals achieved during the X-31A program, including

- * First international X-Program
- * Low cost demonstrator approach realized in stringent time limit
- * Successful application of true workshare and a multi design criteria concept
- * New flight regime cleared for carefree handling without structural limitations
- * First controlled entry into poststall flights
- * First trimmed maneuvers in the poststall flight regime
- * Superior tactical results against state of the art conventional aircrafts
- * First X-aircraft achieving more than 100 test flights in one year

To date the feasibility of controlled flight past the stall barrier has been shown.

Advantages from this program might also influence future work in flight mechanics research of civil aeronautical programs.

[1] Das X-31 Programm, H.Ross und K.Wolf, MBB-UF, Ottobrunn, 1989

[2] X-31 Structural Modelling and Verification, R.Latham and W.Baker, RI, ASME 1990

[3] Taktische Flugerprobung X-31, .Haiplik und R. Gütter, DASA LM, DGLR 1994

